

Probing interfacial interactions: Ionic liquids and cellulose thin films

Lukas Pachernegg-Mair^{a,d}, Jana B. Schaubeder^a, Carina Waldner^a, Anna Mayrhofer^a, Markus Damm^b, Roland Kalb^b, Anna Maria Coclite^c, Ali Khodayari^e, David Seveno^e, Ulrich Hirn^a, Stefan Spirk^{a,d,*}

^a Institute of Bioproducts and Paper Technology, Graz University of Technology, A-8010 Graz, Austria

^b Proionic GmbH, A-8074 Grambach, Austria

^c Institute for Solid State Physics, NAWI Graz, Graz University of Technology, A-8010 Graz, Austria

^d Ecolyte GmbH, Inffeldgasse 21, 8010 Graz, Austria

^e Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, 3001 Leuven, Belgium

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ABSTRACT

The efficient processing of cellulosic materials with ionic liquids heavily relies on the initial contact and wetting phase, which are crucial yet poorly understood in many ionic liquid/cellulose interactions. In this study, we explore these interactions through comprehensive wetting experiments and a robust mathematical framework. By leveraging molecular-kinetic theory (MKT), we illuminate the key factors affecting these interactions, such as viscosity and ion pair volume, and identify specific cellulose chain groups involved in the process. Our findings confirm that ionic liquids selectively adsorb on active sites of cellulose, facilitating a dynamic adsorption-desorption mechanism crucial for forward movement. Notably, we have identified these adsorption sites to be approximately 5 to 20 Å apart, e.g., distances between neighboring C₆-hydroxyl groups within a cellulose molecule. Furthermore, our results demonstrate that the dynamics of jump frequencies are intrinsically linked to the properties of ionic liquids, yet influenced by a complex array of parameters. This study provides significant insights into manipulating the interaction mechanisms to enhance spreading efficiency on surfaces. Our research underscores the pivotal role of cellulose's chemical structure and order, offering valuable implications for improving high-throughput processing techniques in various industrial applications.

1. Introduction

Cellulose is an important feedstock, which is processed in large quantities in different types of biobased industries. Applications range from high volume commodities such as paper products and fibers/textiles, to hygiene and medical products as well as applications in food and biotechnology. Apart from paper and nanocellulose based products, most of the applications require solubilizing the cellulose to enable a shaping process into regenerated fibers or to achieve efficient functionalization. However, this is a major challenge as cellulose is reluctant towards solubilization in common solvents. Nowadays, industrially employed solvents mainly rely on the use of *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide (NMMO)/water, and dimethylacetamide (DMAc)/Lithium chloride (LiCl) while modification via xanthation and to a much smaller extent carbamation is employed. (Cross, Bevan, & Beadle, 1893; Sayyed, Deshmukh, & Pinjari, 2019; Willberg-Keyriläinen, Hiltunen, &

Ropponen, 2018)

The main challenge to address is the amphiphilicity of cellulose, originating from the hydrophobic and hydrophilic faces in the cellulose crystallites. As these crystallites are inaccessible to any solvents due to entropic reasons, the main strategy to dissolve cellulose is to design solvents, which provide a subtle balance between polar (i.e. hydrogen bonding and electrostatics) and non-polar interactions. (Lindman, Karlström, & Stigsson, 2010) In this context, ionic liquids (ILs) have entered the focus of cellulose research to dissolve cellulose and also to act as a reaction medium. (Heinze & Liebert, 2012; Liebert, 2010; Verma et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2006) In general, the dissolution process in ionic liquids is believed to proceed in two stages. Initially, the solvent penetrates between the cellulose crystallites, inducing a swelling of the bulk cellulose. The second step involves entanglement where electron donor-acceptor complexes are formed. This happens preferentially between the hydroxyl groups at the C₆ and C₃ positions of adjacent cellulose chains,

* Corresponding author at: Institute of Bioproducts and Paper Technology, Graz University of Technology, A-8010 Graz, Austria.

E-mail address: stefan.spirk@tugraz.at (S. Spirk).

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leading to the separation of these groups. (Ghasemi, Alexandridis, & Tsianou, 2018; Kosan, Michels, & Meister, 2008) Recent studies reveal that the introduction of specific ionic liquids, so-called saccharide-based ILs (SILs), can significantly disrupt hydrogen bonds in cellulose. (Qiao et al., 2024) These findings align with molecular simulations by Yang et al. (2021) showing that SILs, particularly those containing chloride ions, facilitate polysaccharide thermoplasticization by disrupting the strong inter- and intramolecular interactions.

However, the dissolution process and the role of ILs is still not fully understood. (Bodachivskiy et al., 2020) Efficient ILs for cellulose dissolution purpose include cations like methylpyridinium or methylimidazolium and anions such as chloride, acetate, or formate. (Pinkert, Marsh, Pang, & Staiger, 2009; Remsing, Swatloski, Rogers, & Moyna, 2006) Further, even numbers of the side chains on the cation seem to enhance the solubility of cellulose between C_2 and C_{20} , reaching a maximum at C_4 (Erdmenger, Haensch, Hooogenboom, & Schubert, 2007; Feng & Chen, 2008).

These findings were employed in the development of novel fiber spinning processes, relying on ILs as demonstrated by Sixta and coworkers in the so-called Ioncell® process (Chen, Sawada, Hummel, Sixta, & Budtova, 2020; Michud et al., 2015; Stepan, Michud, Hellstén, Hummel, & Sixta, 2016) and the HighPerCell® process introduced by Hermanutz and coworkers (Ota et al., 2023). Both processes are on the edge of being scaled up, with recycling of the ILs from the spinning bath still being the major challenge. In addition, there are other research lines aiming at using ILs in separating the polymeric cell wall components in wood. Furthermore, SILs have been designed in order to enhance specific properties (hydrophobicity and mechanical) of polysaccharides e. g., starch, via supramolecular interactions. These ILs show potential for adaptation in cellulose processing (Qiao et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2021).

For all these processes, a particular challenge is to better understand the wetting and penetration behavior of ILs in biomass materials. It is obvious that the initial interaction between the biomass surface and the IL plays a crucial role for its dissolution and processing. However, the interactions at the interface are difficult to explore as only a few techniques are available for quantification (e.g., isothermal calorimetry titration).

Here, we tackle this challenge by connecting molecular-kinetic theory and wettability studies of ILs with model cellulosic materials. We hypothesize based on experimental data that ionic liquid molecules, when spreading on cellulose, adhere to active sites of the cellulose macromolecules and desorb to move forward. Therefore, the molecular structure of cellulose is the main influencing factor on the distance an ionic liquid pair is moving forward during spreading. Further we hypothesize based on experimental evidence and theoretical modeling, that the adsorption and desorption frequency is mainly governed by the liquid itself, rather than by the cellulose surface. We provide first evidences that there is a correlation between jump lengths and distances in the molecular structure of cellulose.

Before we move on with the experimental part, the background for the work on molecular-kinetic theory is given.

2. Background

A liquid drop on a surface will spread spontaneously towards its equilibrium contact angle θ^0 [°], which represents the state of minimum free energy (Drelich et al., 2020). Resistance against the spreading arises from viscous friction in the bulk of the liquid and/or molecular friction at the contact line (De Coninck and Blake, 2008). The modeling of a drop spreading on a surface can be realized with different models. These models can be categorized into empirical and non-empirical.

For example, a force balance (capillary force, the gravitational force and a viscous friction force) can be used to describe the wetting of a surface by a liquid drop. (Härth & Schubert, 2012) Common models are the molecular-kinetic theory (MKT) (Blake & De Coninck, 2002; Blake & Haynes, 1969), the hydrodynamics model (HD), the combined MKT-HD

models of De Ruijter model and Petrov and Petrov, the Cahn-Hillard-van der Waals theory, the interface formation model and the precursor-film theory. (De Coninck, de Ruijter, & Voué, 2001; Mohammad Karim, 2022; Mohammad Karim, Fujii, & Kavehpour, 2021; Seveno et al., 2009) Further, molecular dynamics (MD) is used to better understand the underlying mechanism controlling the liquid/solid interaction at the nanoscale particularly through the concept of contact-line friction. (Blake, Fernandez-Toledano, Doyen, & De Coninck, 2015; Fernandez-Toledano, Blake, & De Coninck, 2017, 2019; Lukyanov & Likhtan, 2016) These models explicitly explore molecular interactions at the microscopic scale. MD simulations have therefore been employed to validate or assess the consistency of the MKT e.g., comparing jump frequencies and lengths derived from MKT to those directly obtained from MD simulations. (De Coninck & Blake, 2008; Seveno, Dinter, & De Coninck, 2010; Zhao & Cheng, 2017) This comparison has shown good agreement for fibers and droplets spreading on flat surfaces (Bertrand, Blake, & De Coninck, 2009; De Ruijter, Blake, & De Coninck, 1999; Seveno, Ogonowski, & De Coninck, 2004) and further emphasizes the validity of the MKT.

Previous studies by Delcheva, Ralston, Beattie, and Krasowska (2015) and Li, Sedev, and Ralston (2011), conducted with various ionic liquids on gold, glass and fluoropolymer, showed that the HD-model gives unreasonable results, especially for higher spreading velocities. One possible explanation is that during the spontaneous spreading of ionic liquids, the contact line advances due to the movement of individual ion pairs rather than clusters of molecules. This behavior results in significant energy dissipation at the contact line and not in the bulk of the liquid, which would be a prerequisite for the use of the hydrodynamic model. (Li et al., 2011; Mohammad Karim, 2022) Caused by this, combined models and other models described before may not be suitable or increase mathematical complexity. The MKT, applied here to interpret experimental data, is characterized by the molecular activity occurring at the fluid interface near the contact line. This activity includes surface movement within the fluid as well as interactions with the bulk phase. (Blake & De Coninck, 2002; Blake & Haynes, 1969) The movement of the contact line is described in the model by adsorption of molecules of the so called adsorption sites on the surface of the solid and simultaneous desorption of liquid molecules (Fig. 1, Eq. (1)). (Blake & Haynes, 1969) The frequency with which this adsorption occurs is denoted with κ_w^0 [Hz] in its most general form. The distance between two adsorption sites is denoted with λ [m]. It is assumed that the adsorption sites are evenly distributed on the surface of the solid.

$$v = 2\kappa_w^0 \lambda \sinh\left(\frac{\gamma_{LV} \lambda^2}{k_B T} (\cos\theta^0 - \cos\theta_d)\right) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the contact angle and individual molecules jumping with the frequency κ_w^0 along the surface adsorption sites with a distance of λ .

In this equation (Eq. (1)), v [$m s^{-2}$] represents the spreading velocity, γ_{LV} [$N m^{-1}$] is the surface tension of the liquid against air, k_B [$J K^{-1}$] is the Boltzmann constant, T [K] the absolute temperature, θ^0 [$^\circ$] the equilibrium contact angle and θ_d [$^\circ$] the dynamic contact angle.

This first approach does not take viscosity into account as an influencing factor of the drop spreading. Therefore, Blake and De Coninck (2002) adapted the theory to accommodate liquid viscosity. The activation free energy of wetting ΔG_w^* (Eq. (2)), which is connected to the adsorption frequency κ_w^0 by Eq. (3), can be separated into surface and viscous contributions, ΔG_s^* and ΔG_v^* , respectively.

$$\Delta G_w^* = \Delta G_s^* + \Delta G_v^* \quad (2)$$

$$\kappa_w^0 = \frac{k_B \cdot T}{h} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta G_w^*}{N \cdot k_B \cdot T}\right) \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (2) (Eq. (2)), N is the Avogadro's constant [mol^{-1}] and h is the Planck's length [m]. ΔG_v^* is directly connected with the viscosity of the liquid η_L [$Pa s$], by Eq. (4) (Eq. (4)).

$$\eta_L = \frac{h}{v_L} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta G_v^*}{N k_B T}\right) \quad (4)$$

where v_L is the volume of the 'unit of flow' [m^3]. The surface contribution ΔG_s^* can be expressed with Eq. (5) (Eq. (5)):

$$\kappa_s^0 = \frac{k_B \cdot T}{h} \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta G_s^*}{N k_B T}\right) \quad (5)$$

In addition, κ_s^0 can be calculated directly from $k_{w,0}$ (Eq. (6)) by using the Eqs. (2), (3) and (4) (Eqs. (2)–(4)):

$$\kappa_w^0 = \frac{k_B T}{\eta_L v_L} \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta G_s^*}{N k_B T}\right) = \kappa_s^0 \left(\frac{h}{\eta_L v_L}\right) \quad (6)$$

Combining the Eqs. (1) and (6) (Eq. (1), Eq. (6)) leads to (Eq. (7)):

$$\nu = \frac{2 \kappa_s^0 h \lambda}{\eta_L v_L} \sinh\left[\frac{\gamma_{LV} \lambda^2}{2 k_B T} (\cos\theta^0 - \cos\theta_d)\right] \quad (7)$$

This equation takes the viscosity directly into account and can describe the spreading velocity in relation to the dynamic contact angle (Eq. (7)). Please note that the values of most parameters in this equation (Eq. (7)) can be obtained experimentally, which includes the viscosity of the liquid η_L , the surface tension of the liquid γ_{LV} , the static θ^0 and dynamic contact angle θ_d and the temperature T . The unit of flow v_L [m^3] can be determined further experimentally if we assume that it is the volume of the ion pair (combined volume of anion and cation) that moves along the surface of the substrate. We argue that the strong interaction between cation and anion makes it a plausible hypothesis. The remaining two constants κ_s^0 [Hz] and λ [m] can be determined by fitting experimental data of drop spreading experiments (dynamic contact angle and contact line velocity). Hereby the jump length λ needs to be in the nanometer range for a physical interpretation.

In addition to the calculation of the molecular-kinetic theory, we also employed the hydrodynamic model in our calculations. A more detailed description of the model as well as the data can be found in the supporting information.

Using ILs (1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide [HMIM][NTf₂], 1-dodecyl-3-methyl imidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [DDMIM][NTf₂] and 1-octyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoro methylsulfonyl)imide [OMIM][NTf₂]) and a silicone oil, respectively, Delcheva, Beattie, Ralston, and Krasowska (2018) and Hoffman (1975) suggest that the jump length is not independent of the used liquid (Fig. 2). However, Duvivier et al. (2011) published a comprehensive study on using different mixtures of water and glycerol on glass. Despite the drastic change in the physicochemical properties of the mixture, the jump length seems to be consistent for the liquids. This would support the claim of a jump length solely dependent on the surface. This discrepancy may be due to the

Fig. 2. Literature values for the jump frequency κ^0 and the jump length λ for various liquids on a glass substrate. glycerol – glycerol; sil. – silicon; lv – low viscosity; hv – high viscosity; [●] (Duvivier, Seveno, Rioboo, Blake, & De Coninck, 2011) [★] (Hoffman, 1975) [◆] (Delcheva et al., 2018).

different measurement techniques for the contact angles. (Kirk, Strobel, Lyons, & Janis, 2019; Krishnan et al., 2005; Löblein, Merz, Müller, Kopnarski, & Mücklich, 2022) Further, the composition of the glass, used as a substrate by Delcheva et al. (2018), Hoffman (1975), and Duvivier et al. (2011), its production method used as well as the cleaning procedure may influence its surface chemistry and along with it the distance between individual adsorption sites. (Carter & Norton, 2007; Onodera et al., 2020) These combined effects may be the reason for the difference in these published data.

Delcheva et al. (2018) suggests that both substrate-ionic liquid and water-ionic liquid interactions significantly contribute to the wetting process mechanisms as well as the size of the ionic liquid molecules. Further, we would argue that complex fluorine-fluorine interactions may additionally influence the spreading kinetics by the formation of fluorophilic domains and complexing interactions. (Brehm, Pulst, Kressler, & Sebastiani, 2019; Pereiro et al., 2013; Rauber, Heib, Schmitt, & Hempelmann, 2016; Tsuzuki, 2012) This may further influence the jump length values and increases deviation.

3. Experimental

3.1. Materials

1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium acrylate [BMIM][ACR], 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate [BMIM][OAc], 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acrylate [EMIM][ACR], 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium diethylphosphate [EMIM][DEP], 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate [EMIM][OAc], 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium octanoate [EMIM][OOc], 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium propionate [EMIM][OPr], 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide [EMIM][TFSI] and 1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium acrylate [HEXMIM][ACR] were supplied by proionic GmbH (Grambach, Austria). 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide [EMIM][DCA] was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). *n*-heptane (ROTIPURAN® 99 %) for surface tension measurements, chloroform (CHCl₃, stabilized with about 0.6 % ethanol) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30 % in water) were obtained from Carl-Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany). Hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37 %) was purchased from VWR Chemicals (Vienna, Austria) and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄, ≥95 %) was purchased from Fisher Scientific (United Kingdom). All chemicals were used as received. Trimethylsilyl cellulose (TMSC, prepared by silylation of Avicel, degree of substitution $DS_{Si} = 2.74$, molecular weight $M_w = 181,000 g \cdot mol^{-1}$, polydispersity index $PDI = 6.1$, determined by

size exclusion chromatography in chloroform) was obtained from TITK (Rudolstadt, Germany). Silicon wafers with a thickness of $675 \pm 25 \mu\text{m}$ were purchased from Siegert Wafers (Aachen, Germany).

3.2. Thin film preparation

Thin films have been prepared according to Kontturi, Thüne, and Niemantsverdriet (2003b), but in brief: In a typical procedure, TMSC was dissolved in chloroform (0.75 wt%) in an ultrasonic bath for 4–6 h until no solid particles are visible any more. The milky solution was filtered with a $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ PTFE filter. Silicon wafers were cut into $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}$ slides and cleaned with piranha solution H_2O_2 (30 wt%)/ H_2SO_4 (1:2 v/v) for 30 min, followed by vigorous washing with deionized water. Wafers were dried with a stream of nitrogen. The clear TMSC solution was deposited via spin coating ($80 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, $t = 60 \text{ s}$ with a spinning speed = 4000 rpm, acceleration = $2500 \text{ rpm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) onto the cleaned silicon wafers. The TMSC was subsequently regenerated by exposing the films to HCl vapor (generated from diluted HCl solution of 10 %) for 14 min (Fig. 3) (Mohan et al., 2012).

3.3. Methods

3.3.1. Wettability and surface tension of the ILs

The contact angle of ILs on the surface was measured with an optical contact angle goniometers (OCA200, Dataphysics, Filderstadt, Germany). The cellulose thin films were equilibrated in a climatized room ($23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 50 % R.H., according to ISO 187) at least 24 h prior to use. Liquid drops ($2 \mu\text{L}$) were dispensed with an automatic dosing unit (SD-DM, Dataphysics, Filderstadt, Germany) using a medical 1 mL single use syringe and single use medical tips (B Braun, Melsungen, Germany) with 0.4 and 0.8 mm internal diameter depending on liquid viscosities. The surface was lifted towards the droplet, to minimize inertia at the impact. Liquid drops were recorded with a high-speed camera at 100 frames per second. The start of the data collection ($t = 0 \text{ s}$) was set to the point, at which the droplet has no contact left with the tip and is solely in contact with the surface. The contact angle was analyzed with the SCA20 (v 5.0.32 build 5032) software package from Dataphysics (Filderstadt, Germany). Ellipse fitting was used as calculation algorithm to gather contact angle, drop height and diameter information. At least 5 measurements per ionic liquid were performed and averaged before further

calculations. Further analysis was done with MATLAB® R2020b (MathWorks Inc., USA).

Interfacial tension was obtained with a Dataphysics OCA200 (Dataphysics, Germany). The pendant drop method was employed with a 1.83 mm diameter tip (Dataphysics, Filderstadt, Germany) on a medical syringe. The liquid was dosed with an automated liquid dosing unit. Drop size was measured in air (climatized laboratory according to ISO 187, $23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 50 % R.H.) and *n*-heptane as surrounding medium in a custom-made setup. The drop size was determined via Laplace-Young fitting. At least five measurements per ionic liquid and surrounding medium were performed and averaged. For a more comprehensive explanation of the procedure, we refer to our previous work (Pachernegg et al., 2024).

3.3.2. Atomic force microscopy

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were acquired with a Tosca™ 400 atomic force microscope (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) using silicon cantilevers (AP-ARROW-NCR from NanoWorld AG, Neuchatel, Switzerland) with a resonance frequency of 285 kHz, a force constant of 42 Nm, and a nominal tip radius $< 10 \text{ nm}$. Images were taken in tapping mode. Data processing and image analysis was done with Gwyddion v2.60 software.

3.3.3. Attenuated total reflection infrared spectroscopy

The attenuated total reflection infrared spectroscopy (ATR-IR) spectra were recorded using a Bruker Alpha-P Diamond ATR spectrometer from the regenerated cellulose thin films with the accompanied OPUS software package. The analysis was performed using Origin software (OriginLab Corporation, USA).

3.3.4. Data fitting

We determined the molecular jump length λ and the jump frequency κ_s^0 of different ionic liquids by fitting those parameters to the molecular-kinetic theory (Eq. (7)) using data of the drop spreading experiments (this includes contact angle as well as drop size vs. time, which is used to calculate the drop spreading velocity). Fitting to Eq. (7) (Eq. (7)) was done with MATLAB® R2020b (MathWorks Inc., USA) and its incorporated Nonlinearleastsquare-fitting function and its Simplex-algorithm to enable the use of boundary constraints.

In a first fitting experiment, we tried to validate the hypothesis that

Fig. 3. Spin coating process of the cellulose thin films. (A) Dropping of the TMSC solution on the silicon wafer, (B) spinning of the wafer, (C) evaporation of the solvent, (D) TMSC film without solvent, (E) cleavage of the trimethyl silyl groups with HCl vapor, (F) regenerated cellulose thin film.

the molecular jump length is solely defined by the cellulose substrate. Hence, we fitted the data for an overall jump length λ , which is the same constant value for all experiments. The values for the jump length λ have been set to a fixed range of $0.01 \leq \lambda \leq 25 \text{ \AA}$. The jump frequency κ_s^0 from the first step was used as a starting value to find the optimum jump frequency κ_s^0 for every liquid at every jump length λ . To find overall λ the error of each individual sample ($R_1^2, R_2^2, \dots, R_n^2$) at each jump length step ($R^2(\lambda = 0.1) = \sum R_{n,\lambda=0.1}$) was summed up to calculate a mean R^2 -error for each jump length λ . The overall jump length λ is the one with minimum mean- R^2 error. The calculation procedure is schematically shown in Fig. S3. Calculation data is shown in the ESI (Fig. S4 to S13).

In a second step, minimum R^2 fitting (See eq. S2 in the ESI) of λ and κ_s^0 was done for each individual sample (IL_1, IL_2, \dots, IL_n) and its repetitions ($IL_1: T_{IL1,1}, T_{IL1,2}, \dots, T_{IL1,n}; n \geq 5$) to find the optimal values for the frequency and the jump length for each IL and its repetitions without any constraints. The displayed data in this work, represents the average of this repetitions. Individual values can be found in the ESI.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Cellulose film preparation and characterization

We chose as a cellulosic model system, thin films derived from trimethylsilyl cellulose (TMSC), where we have vast knowledge about chain alignment, amorphicity, water/humidity uptake and interaction with different types of materials such as proteins, polysaccharides and paper chemicals. TMSC has proven to provide homogenous thin films by spin coating, which can be easily converted to cellulose via vapor phase HCl treatment as well as by UV light in presence of a photoacid generator (Fig. 3, A-F). (Kontturi, Thüne, & Niemantsverdriet, 2003a; Wolfberger, Kargl, Griesser, & Spirk, 2014) The resulting films have a low roughness and have been employed in a wide range of application such as bio interfaces, and advanced materials. (Kontturi & Spirk, 2019; Raghuvanshi & Garnier, 2019; Reishofer et al., 2017; Schaubeder et al., 2022; Wolfberger et al., 2015) The used films have a thickness of ca. 30 nm featuring a roughness of ca 1.5 nm in this study as determined by AFM (Fig. 4, A and B). The AFM phase images are available in the supporting information (Fig. S3, A and B). ATR-IR spectroscopy confirms the conversion of the TMSC to cellulose as the related bands (δ_{SiC} at $875\text{--}750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, δ_{Si-O-C} at 1251 cm^{-1}) disappear concomitant with the appearance of the OH stretching vibrations typical for cellulose at $3200\text{--}3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. S2). In the next step, the contact angles and the wetting dynamics of 10 ionic liquids were determined and investigated with the HD-theory (see supporting information for calculation) and MKT using the experimental data (Fig. 5 and Fig. S4 to S13).

4.2. Molecular-kinetic theory

As mentioned in the background, the jump length is interpreted as the distance between individual adsorption sites of the surface and

Fig. 5. Experimental spreading data of [EMIM][ACR] on a cellulose thin film.

should theoretically be independent of the used liquids. (Berg, 1993; Blake & Haynes, 1969; Mohammad Karim, 2022) Therefore we do not need to distinguish between the ILs and can fit all to obtain the jump length on cellulose. In a first step, the jump frequency was fitted to the experimental data, using jump lengths between $0 \leq \lambda \leq 25 \text{ \AA}$. The selection of values was done by the intramolecular distances within individual cellulose macromolecules as well as the intermolecular spacing between adjacent molecules. The determined jump lengths are shown in Fig. 6 (Fig. 6) as a function of R^2 errors over all ionic liquids.

Calculation of the mean R^2 -error with a fixed jump length revealed that the best fit for all ionic liquids is at a jump length of around $\lambda = 9 \text{ \AA}$. This distance is in the same order of magnitude as the distance of two hydroxy groups at the C6 carbon in a single cellulose chain (Fig. 7), which is around 10.4 \AA . (Moreira, Weber, & Poma, 2022; Nishiyama, Sugiyama, Chanzy, & Langan, 2003) As shown already by Jones et al. (2020) there is a 2D arrangement rather than a 3D arrangement in regenerated cellulose film. Consequently, Fig. 7 (Fig. 7) should be regarded solely as a conceptual representation of various potential pathways.

Since the C6-hydroxy groups usually feature better accessibility than others in the cellulose chain, it makes sense that this group is the main contributor to the available adsorption sites (Fig. 7). (Heinze & Liebert, 2001; Lim et al., 2015; Verlhac, Dedier, & Chanzy, 1990) It is likely that the main adsorption sites for ILs moving on the substrate is along the cellulose macromolecule by jumping from one C6 hydroxy group to the adjacent one within the same chain. The results support our hypothesis of a movement of single IL molecules along the cellulose by interacting with the hydroxy group most likely available for this interaction. This result is in agreement with the original publication of Blake et al. and computational models, which suggest that the droplet indeed moves forward by means of single molecule adsorption and desorption on the surface. (Blake, 2006; Blake & De Coninck, 2002; Blake & Haynes, 1969;

Fig. 4. (A) Height AFM image of the TMSC-film after spin-coating on a silicon wafer, (B) height AFM image of the regenerated cellulose thin film on a silicon wafer. Both images were measured in tapping mode.

Fig. 6. Averaged R^2 -error of the investigated ionic liquids on the cellulose thin films. Calculated with default jump length λ values.

Seveno et al., 2010) Although this is the main mechanism, the calculation of each ionic liquid suggests more than one maximum (see detailed information in the supporting information Fig. S5 to S14) and therefore

it is evident that the movement of the contact line proceeds also via other adsorption sites and not strictly along single cellulose macromolecules. For instance, Jones et al. (2020) evidenced that the chosen cellulose thin films show orientation and 2D order of the individual cellulose chains. The distance between the individual chains of cellulose in these 2D ordered domains is similar as in crystalline cellulose (4 Å), where the R^2 -value starts to increase. Below 4 Å, the R^2 -error is relatively low and indicates no significant molecule jumping interactions (see also Table S6). These possible pathways as well as domain boundaries which can be found in such systems may be the reason (Jones et al., 2020).

Additionally, as discussed in literature, cellulose dissolution is believed to be initiated through the strong interaction of the IL anion with the hydroxyl groups of cellulose, particularly at the C₃ and C₆ positions. (Ghasemi et al., 2018; Holding et al., 2017; Kosan et al., 2008; Kraemer, Reyes, Cartes, Mejía, & Rojas, 2024) This means, that the size and chemical nature of the anion has a significant role in the interaction. When considering the size of the anion (Table S2), calculated from crystal data (assuming a spherical shape), the size of all anions is >2.59 Å. This is close to the shown minima, occurring in the calculation (Fig. 6), and may be the structural limitation in the interaction of the anion with the hydroxyl groups and the lower limitation of the jump length.

For jump lengths exceeding 25 Å, achieving a feasible fit proved impossible, which validates our choice of fitting parameters. From a physical standpoint, this implies the absence of single jumps over

Fig. 7. Possible jump paths and lengths along cellulose surfaces for (A) 234432 CNC arrangements with exposed 100, 200, 110, and 1–10 faces, and (B) 34443 arrangements with 010 exposed face. The latter arrangement also includes the jump paths in 234432 structures.”

distances $>25 \text{ \AA}$ between adsorption sites on the cellulose thin film, which can be expected when considering the 2D order of the cellulose thin film. (Jones et al., 2020) The low R^2 values ($R^2 < 0.5$) beyond 15 \AA implies a relatively unlikely jump above this distance on average. Since all the pathways marked in Fig. 6 are smaller than 20 \AA , it would suggest that the IL molecules interact with the nearest available site and do not jump over possible adsorption sites. The asymmetry of the R^2 -values below and exceeding the 9 \AA may be the result of the discussed cellulose structure. Based on this assumption, one can calculate possible movement patterns along the cellulose crystal/chain (Fig. 7). If we now assume that the ionic liquid is likely to interact with the nearest possible interaction site, we see that most possible jump paths are below 10.4 \AA (8.8 \AA , 8.1 \AA , 6.5 \AA , 9.8 \AA and 7.9 \AA) and in a comparable narrow range. This may lead to the sharp rise of the R^2 -value, especially above 5 \AA . Beyond 9 \AA jump paths are less likely to occur (15.8 \AA and 13.2 \AA). The still significant high R^2 -values, may result either from these paths or from irregularities in the order of the cellulose chains, resulting in values outside of these theoretical ranges. In combination, these factors contribute to a less sharp decrease of the R^2 -values beyond 9 \AA . Further also the formation of so-called ionic domains inside the ionic liquid may influence the movement of molecules (Canongia Lopes & Padua, 2006; Opere-Addo et al., 2024; Rozas-Castro, Lodeiro, Contreras, & Ormazábal-Toledo, 2024). Here the size of the anions may again play a significant role, since multiples of the anion volumes easily exceed the size of 9 \AA changing the interaction environment and jump patterns.

The jump frequency is increasing with the volume of the ion pair (Fig. 8, A), with the exception of [EMIM][TFSI]. Additional fluorine-fluorine interactions in the bulk of the liquid [EMIM][TFSI] (Rauber et al., 2016) may influence the spreading and may be the reason for the discrepancy of this liquid. The increase in jump frequency may be related to increased (interaction) surface area of the molecule, its shape or lower energy barriers for the jump caused by stronger and more frequent interactions with the surface (Pannier, Diagne, Spiegel, Hoelzle, & Barton, 2017; Roques-Carmes, Babak, Mathieu, & Gigante, 2013).

As suggested before, these interactions proceed via the hydroxy-C6 group. These interactions mainly rely on hydrogen bonds. The polar part of the surface tension hereby represents the possibility of the ionic liquid for dipole-dipole interactions. (Greaves & Drummond, 2015; Janczuk & Bialopiotrowicz, 1989; Miran, Kinoshita, Yasuda, Susan, & Watanabe, 2011) A higher polar ratio of the ionic liquid would induce stronger interactions between the liquid and the cellulose surface and ultimately leads to a lower jump frequency (Fig. 8, B). A higher polar ratio does indeed lead to a lower jump frequency (Fig. 8, B).

As discussed already above additional fluorine-fluorine interactions may be the reason for the behavior of the [EMIM][TFSI]. The

dicyanamide anion in [EMIM][DCA], represents a pseudohalide (Ghosh et al., 2011), which show strong dipoles caused by their highly delocalized charges. (Hilder et al., 2020) These strong dipoles, are the reason for the high polar ratio of this ionic liquid. Further, dipoles can easily be induced in halides (Cavallo et al., 2016), which also lead to a high dispersive ratio. The combination of a high polar ratio and a high dispersive ratio of the surface tension of this liquid lead to increased self-interaction of the ionic liquid, which may be not adequately represented in the MKT. Additionally, it could also lead to an unfavorable cellulose/IL pairing.

Arguably it would also be possible, that the jump length is in strong correlation with each individual ionic liquid and its specific interactions with the surface. To test this hypothesis, the jump length and the jump frequency were also calculated to obtain the best fit without any constraints to physical boundaries.

The findings revealed a range of jump lengths, with [EMIM][DCA] demonstrating the shortest at $7.6 \pm 0.4 \text{ \AA}$ and [EMIM][TFSI] exhibiting the longest at $14.3 \pm 1.9 \text{ \AA}$, as depicted in Fig. 9. The majority of ionic liquids are clustered within a jump length window of 8 to 12 \AA , providing similar distances as discussed above. This supports the theory that the C6-hydroxy group is the main interaction site of the cellulose and the ionic liquid. If the jump length would be solely a factor of the surface, this calculation would yield a constant jump length value for all ionic liquids. But based on these calculations, it is likely that the variability in jump lengths on cellulose thin films arises not solely from surface characteristics but may also come from the distinct interactions each ionic liquid has with the surface, influenced by its molecular size, viscosity, and surface tension. Further, the trend depicted in Fig. 9, (A) may indicate that as the ion pair volume increases, the ability of the molecule to jump over a greater distance increases as well. This could be due to the increased steric hindrance and reduced mobility of larger ions, leading to greater jump lengths. These results imply that the chemical composition and structural complexity of ionic liquids contribute to their distinct jump lengths, larger molecules showing more pronounced jump lengths. In addition, this increase could also correlate to intermolecular interactions of the ionic liquids itself e.g., ionic domains which can be formed in such systems. (Seduraman, Klähn, & Wu, 2009; Singh & Kumar, 2007; Triolo, Russina, Bleif, & Di Cola, 2007; Wang & Voth, 2006) The complex nature of ILs make it therefore highly complicated to draw definite conclusions and further experimental and computational works are necessary.

In contrast, the jump frequency is intimately linked to the liquid's properties, such as its surface tension. The calculated data shows frequencies ranging from $0.25 \pm 0.14 \text{ GHz}$ for [EMIM][TFSI] to $18.2 \pm 3.2 \text{ GHz}$ for [BMIM][OAc], as illustrated in Fig. 9, B and C. High-frequency

Fig. 8. (A) Jump frequency κ_0^0 of the ionic liquids on cellulose thin films at the fixed jump length of 9 \AA over the volume of the ion pair V_{ion} , (B) jump frequency κ_0^0 of the ionic liquids over the polar ratio of the surface tension. Surface tension values from our previous work. (Pachernegg et al., 2024).

Fig. 9. (A) Jump length λ of the ionic liquids versus their calculated ion pair volumes. (B) Shear viscosity of the individual ionic liquids versus the calculated jump length from experimental data. Measured on cellulose thin films. (C) Jump frequency calculated without constraints against the surface tension of the liquid.

jumps, such as those observed with [BMIM][OAc], imply lower resistance to movement within the system, although [BMIM][OAc] shows a comparable high viscosity. Conversely, lower jump frequencies, such as with [EMIM][TFSI], could indicate that the liquid's internal structure, possibly due to stronger ion-ion or ion-surface interactions, hinders rapid movements. A higher surface tension corresponds to stronger intermolecular interactions, which may influence the jump frequency, as seen with [EMIM][TFSI]. (Pachernegg et al., 2024) This implies that liquids with higher surface tension may create a more stable yet restricted environment for surface interactions, leading to fewer jumps over a given timeframe. In contrast, liquids with lower surface tension, such as [BMIM][OAc], exhibit higher jump frequencies, suggesting that weaker internal forces facilitate easier molecular movement.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion we demonstrated that the chemical structure of cellulose as well as its order plays a role in the spreading of ionic liquid across cellulose surfaces. Our experimental findings, interpreted through the molecular-kinetic theory, support the hypothesis that ionic liquids adsorb to active sites on the cellulose, subsequently desorbing to

facilitate forward movement. Our experimental data analyzed by the MKT suggests, that the distances of this adsorption sites are approximately in the range of 8 to 12 Å, corresponding to characteristic distances in the cellulose macromolecule.

Moreover, our data suggest that the jump frequencies are primarily influenced by the properties of the ionic liquids themselves, confirming our hypothesis on interconnection between IL properties and the jump frequency. This also contributes to a deeper understanding of the molecular interactions at play and how to control these. In the case of the investigated ionic liquids, we demonstrated that the liquids' polar surface tension component is affecting the dynamic jump frequency. Finally, our results support the validity of the MKT-model for the complex liquid-solid pairing of ionic liquids on cellulose.

In summary, our research provides evidence on how ionic liquids interact with cellulose, especially when moving along cellulose thin films. The important role of cellulose's chemical structure and its order in the spreading dynamics of ionic liquids is a key parameter when trying to understand drop movement. Additionally, it provides information on how ionic liquids can be designed for fast spreading kinetic.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lukas Pachernegg-Mair: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jana B. Schaubeder:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Data curation. **Carina Waldner:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Anna Mayrhofer:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Markus Damm:** Data curation. **Roland Kalb:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Anna Maria Coclite:** Writing – review & editing. **Ali Khodayari:** Visualization, Methodology. **David Seveno:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Ulrich Hirn:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Stefan Spirk:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT 4.0 (OpenAI, USA), Perplexity.AI (USA) and Scite.ai (USA) in order to enhance readability, language and search efficiently for scientific data. After using these tools/services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of competing interest

The author is an Editorial Board Member/Editor-in-Chief/Associate Editor/Guest Editor for this journal and was not involved in the editorial review or the decision to publish this article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Additional information in the supporting information includes a calculation procedure for the ion pair volumes and the used volumes for the calculations in this paper (Table S1 and Table S2), as well as the measured water contents of the ionic liquids used in the study (Fig. S1). The contact angle values for water, diiodomethane, ethylene glycol, and glycerol, as reported in the literature and this publication on cellulose thin films, along with ATR-IR measurements of the cellulose thin films, are presented in Fig. S2. (Fig. S2). The calculation procedure for the MKT is represented in Fig. S3 (Fig. S3). Further provided are a literature review table on published values of the MKT model (Table S3) as well as the used physical properties of the ionic liquids (Table S4) and the calculation of the HD model (Table S5). The phase AFM images of the

cellulose thin film are attached (Fig. S4). Calculated values of the MKT, for each ionic liquid can be seen in table S6 (Table S6) and following figures (Fig. S5 to S14). Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2025.123356>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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